

EVALUATION OF VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES USING AN INDENTATION TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Creep behavior of a polymer matrix composite and two metal matrix composites were studied using an indentation technique. In particular, the materials tested were chopped glass fibers in nylon, aluminum oxide particles in aluminum and silicon carbide whiskers in aluminum. As part of indentation technique, sheet specimens were placed on a massive substrate and subjected to step loading by an indenter with a spherical tip. The resulting vertical deformation of the indenter was measured with time. For the polymer matrix composite a master creep compliance curve was obtained. A material parameter identification model was developed to back calculate creep properties for the two metal matrix composites.

Keywords: Viscoelasticity, indentation, creep, polymer matrix, metal matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the development of composite materials tailored to specific applications, it is very desirable to have access to a simple test method for the evaluation of their mechanical properties that does not require elaborate specimen preparation nor the need for gripping. In addition, it is also desirable to have a relatively simple apparatus to test samples. The indentation technique fulfills the above requirements and is used extensively to measure various types of mechanical properties. For instance, the dynamic indentation method has been used effectively to determine the high strain rate and flow behavior of ductile materials(1). Fracture toughness measurement of ceramic materials were made using the indentation technique(2,3). The need for the characterization of the mechanical properties of thin films has generated considerable interest in microhardness and submicron indentation devices(4). Recently indentation test method has been used to characterize the rheological properties of asphalts(5). In this paper viscoelastic properties of a polymer matrix composite is studied for a range of temperatures using the indentation technique. Master creep compliance curves were obtained using the time temperature equivalence hypothesis. In addition, creep properties of two metal matrix composites have been also studied using the technique.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Apparatus

Figure 1 shows the schematic of the indentation test apparatus developed for the evaluation of viscoelastic properties of composite materials. The specimen in the form of thin film or a thickplate resting or bonded to a massive substrate is used in the evaluation of properties. The specimen is indented by an indenter of spherical or conical tip. For reducing the effect of substrate mechanical properties on the measured properties of test materials, it is necessary to

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Indentation Setup

have the indentation depths much smaller than the thickness of the sample. The load and indentation depths were measured by a load cell and a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) respectively. The specimen was enclosed in a thermal chamber in which any desirable temperature within a range of 25-600°C could be maintained during the test. The step loading needed in the creep test was obtained by operating a Bellofram load cylinder connected to a compressed air supply via a solenoid valve. The solenoid valve in turn is controlled by a pulsing unit which can be set to produce a load pulse of a desirable duration.

2.2 Materials Tested

Creep properties of three different types of composites were studied as part of this investigation. These were composites made up of chopped glass fibers in Nylon matrix (20 percent chopped glass fibers), aluminum oxide particles in aluminum matrix (15 percent aluminum particles) and the silicon carbide whiskers dispersed in aluminum matrix (20 percent Sic Whiskers).

2.3 Experimental Procedure and Results

Sheet specimens (0.025 m. length, 0.013 m. wide and 0.003 m. thick) of the three test materials were placed on a massive block of steel and indented by a cylindrical rod (diameter 0.006m) with a spherical tip. Creep tests were conducted by subjecting specimens to step loading of various magnitudes and measuring the vertical deformation of the indenter with time. Creep behavior of Glass/Nylon Composite was studied for four magnitudes of vertical load and temperature. Figure 2 shows a typical indenter displacement versus time curve obtained from a creep test for a

Figure 2. Indenter Displacement Versus Time Curve for Glass/Nylon Composite

load of 201N and a temperature of 81°C. In Figure 3 are shown the displacement versus time curves obtained from the experimental data for the aluminum oxide particles in aluminum (Al₂O₃(P)/Al) for three loads and a temperature of 197°C. Figure 4 shows the corresponding indentation displacement curves for silicon carbide whiskers in aluminum matrix (SiC (W)/Al) for various loads and a temperature of 94°C. In the same figure are shown creep curves for the aluminum matrix material for comparison.

Figure 3. Indenter Displacement Versus Time Curves for Al₂O₃ (p)/AL Composite

Figure 4. Indenter Displacement Versus Time Curves for SiC(w)/Al Composite and Aluminum Matrix

3. THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The contact analysis of a spherical indenter pressed against a semi infinite linear viscoelastic medium was originally performed by Lee and Radok(6). According to this analysis the vertical displacement of the indenter for a time dependent vertical force P(t) on the indenter is given by

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_0^t J(t-t') \frac{dP(t')}{dt'} dt' = \frac{8}{3} \sqrt{R} [\delta(t)]^2 \quad (1)$$

- where
- J(t) = Creep Compliance in shear
 - P(t) = applied time dependent load
 - R = radius of spherical indenter
 - δ(t) = time dependent vertical displacement of the indenter
 - t = time

For a steploding P(t) = P₀H(t) (where H(t) Heaviside step function) equation (1) reduces to

$$[\delta(t)]^2 = \frac{3}{16\sqrt{R}} J(t) P_0 H(t) \quad (2)$$

The stress analysis of an elastic plate resting on a semi infinite medium(7) indicated that the selection of proper thickness of the plate, elastic properties of the semi-infinite medium and the size of the indenter is important to reduce the influence of the substrate properties. Table 1 shows the proper selection of the geometrical parameters of the plate specimen and the material parameters of the substrate for three types of indenters that is required to obtain simple semi-infinite solution for the plate in the investigation of mechanical properties.

Table 1. Relationship of the thickness of the sample, the radius of the indenter and vertical displacement of the indenter

		Cylindrical	Conical	Spherical
$\beta = G/G_s$	$\beta < 1$	$R > h / 19$	$\alpha > \tan\left(\frac{\pi h}{3.8 \delta}\right)$	$R > h^2 / 36.1 \delta$
	$\beta = 1$	$R = h / 19$	$\alpha = \tan\left(\frac{\pi h}{3.8 \delta}\right)$	$R = h^2 / 36.1 \delta$
	$\beta > 1$	$R < h / 19$	$\alpha < \tan\left(\frac{\pi h}{3.8 \delta}\right)$	$R < h^2 / 36.1 \delta$

R=the radius of the cylindrical and spherical indenter
 α =the half-angle of the conical indenter
h=the thickness of the sample
 δ =the vertical displacement of the indenter

For the range of loads and temperature the indentation test data on glass/Nylon composite material showed that the material response is linear viscoelastic in nature. The elastic analysis of a thin plate on a semi infinite medium subjected to a contact load by a spherical indenter developed elsewhere(7) was modified to obtain the solution (5) for a viscoelastic plate resting on a semi-infinite elastic medium. Based upon this analysis the expression for shear creep compliance can be shown to be

$$J(t) = \frac{16\sqrt{R}}{3P_0} f(R, \delta, h) [\delta(t)]^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (3)$$

- P_0 = stepload applied to the specimen by the indenter
- R = radius of the indenter
- h = thickness of the sample
- δ = verticle displacement of the indenter
- J(t) = shear creep compliance of the composite
- f = a function of the radius of the tip and the depth of the indenter and the thickness of the sample.

The function f is expressed as an integral and is to be evaluated numerically. The function f reduces to unity when the thickness of the sample is large compared to the indentation radius and the depth of indenter. When the function f becomes one, the expression for the creep compliance (equation 3) reduces to the solution for a linear semi-infinite viscoelastic medium (6). Creep behaviour of the metal matrix composites investigated here was modeled according to a multiaxial theory of creep for particle strengthened composites developed by Zhu and Weng (9).

the constitutive relations for the composites according to this theory for the transient creep and steady creep regions respectively are given by

$$\dot{\epsilon}_t^c = b \left\{ d \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -p \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{c_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 2 \right]^2 r \right\} \right] \sigma^{*n} - \epsilon^{*c} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s^c = a \left\{ \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -p \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{c_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 2 \right]^2 r \right\} \right] \sigma^{*n} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where

c_1 = volume concentrations of inclusions

r = particle size of inclusions

a, b, c, d and n are material parameters of the matrix

$$\sigma^* = \left(\frac{3}{2} S_{ij} S_{ij} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and $\epsilon^{*c} = \left(\frac{2}{3} S_{ij} S_{ij} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$

S_{ij} = deviatoric stress tensor

ϵ_{ij} = strain tensor

Using equations (1) and (2) in a material parameter identification model which used a finite element sub model in conjunction with the Conmin optimization scheme (9) the creep constitutive parameters were obtained. The finite element submodel was used to analyse the stresses and strains in a thin plate resting on an elastic substrate (See Figure 5). In Figure 6 is given the flow chart for the material parameter identification model.

Figure 5. Plate on a Rigid Semi-infinite Medium

Figure 6. Flowchart for prediction of constitutive materials parameters

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Equation (3) was used to determine the creep compliance versus time curves from the observed indentation depth versus time and temperatures data for the glass/Nylon composite. The creep compliance curves for the glass/Nylon Composite for four temperatures (28, 38, 49 and 81°C), are shown in Figure 7. The creep compliance curves at various temperatures were then shifted using the well known time-temperature shift hypothesis to construct the master creep compliance

Figure 7. Creep Compliance Versus Time Curves for Glass/Nylon Composite

versus reduced time curve for the glass/Nylon composite material (See Figure 8). The master creep compliance curve represents the creep behavior for an extended time scale at the selected reference temperature. The shift factor that was used to construct the master curve is a function of temperature and is found to conform to the well known WLF equation (10) (See Figure 9). The material parameter identification model described earlier was used to determine the constitutive parameters based upon equations (4) and (5). In table 2 are given the constitutive parameters that characterize the creep properties of Al₂O₃ (P)/Al and SiC(W)/Al metal matrix composites. In Figures 3 and 4 are shown the indenter depth variation with time for the metal matrix composites evaluated from equations (4) and (5) and the constants given in table 2. The predicted curves fit the experimental data very well.

The indentation technique can be used effectively in the evaluation of constitutive parameters provided the proper size of the indenter and the indentation depth in relation to the thickness of the sample are chosen to reduce the influence of the substrate properties on the measured properties of the test material. Figure 10 indicates that for the indentation depth and the size of the indenter used creep properties of glass/Nylon are not influenced by the substrate properties.

Figure 8 Master creep compliance curve for Glass/Nylon

Figure 9 Shift factor for Glass/Nylon composite

Table 2. Material parameters for composites

	a	b	d	n	p
SiC(w)/AL	3.4E-7	9.582	6.5E-5	0.3896	0.135
Al ₂ O ₃ (p)/AL	2.7E-7	11.273	8.6E-5	0.4130	0.257

Figure 10 Creep Composite for Glass/Nylon Composite

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